

THEORETICAL EXPRESSION OF THE CONCEPT OF MARKETING SERVICE

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Annotation: *This article covers the activities of the marketing department service that promotes the entry of local products and services into the world market and current issues in this area, as well as brief solutions and suggestions to these problems.*

Keywords: *marketing, marketing services, marketing activities, purpose.*

Like any fast-growing industry and sector today, the marketing industry is rapidly evolving in every region and region. Is the marketing department performing its functions and responsibilities well enough, or is the marketing service well organized in the enterprise? Questions like these often go unanswered. To find out, researchers, researchers and industry insiders are doing research on how well a marketing service is implemented in an enterprise. So what is a marketing service?

Marketing services are a set of activities of a group, association, department and management of specially trained marketers. Marketing services serve consumers and act in their best interests. Improving economic performance; find ways to make the company more profitable; analysis of market capacity and opportunities; The main activities of marketing services are the balance of supply and demand, the collection of information on the elements of price and market, the improvement of goods, the organization of advertising.

Marketing services are also involved in setting standards for the use of live and generalized human resources; organizes the rational sale of goods, solves the issues of logistics; analyzes the economic and technical condition of industry, agriculture and other sectors; participates in determining the near and long-term prospects of the enterprise, operatively organizes production from a marketing point of view; high levels of labor and remuneration. At the same time, it is necessary to clarify the concept of marketing strategy for the organization and forecasting of marketing services.

A marketing strategy is a firm that describes how a particular element should use the opportunities and resources at its disposal to achieve the greatest results and increase profitability in the long run. In fact, it is a general plan of action in the field of marketing, with the help of which the company expects to achieve its marketing goals. This means setting specific goals for each individual product, market type, for a specific period. The strategy is formed in the framework of general production and commercial activities in accordance with the individual capabilities of a particular enterprise and the characteristics of market conditions.

The enterprise must create a marketing system that carries out all marketing activities and planning. If it's a small business, one person should do the marketing. He conducts marketing research, organizes sales and advertising, and provides customer service. If the business is large, the marketing department will be in charge of marketing services.

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The most common type of marketing service organization is the functional type, in which marketing professionals direct the various tasks of marketing activities. They report to the Vice President (Deputy Director) for Marketing.

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Procurement for the needs of the enterprise is the process of determining the need for specific products, evaluating and selecting

products of a specific brand, and making a decision based on the choice of one of the suppliers available in the market.

The advantage of a functional service is its ease of management. At the same time, with the expansion of the product range and the enterprise market, the effectiveness of this scheme decreases, it becomes difficult to develop a plan for each individual market, it becomes difficult to regulate the entire marketing activity.

A marketing mix is a combination of four components: product, price, distribution, and sales promotion. In order to carry out all marketing activities, it is necessary to create four systems in production - marketing information, marketing planning, organization of marketing services and creation of marketing control. All of this makes up the marketing management process.

When service companies think about marketing strategies, they usually think of outbound and direct methods, i.e., direct referrals to prospective customers and clients. review messages. The goal in this approach is to be convincing and engaging so that your audience can respond and participate in the service offered.

As long as marketing exists, these methods will undoubtedly be on trend. But service marketing strategies have evolved over the years, especially since the advent of digital marketing. The behavior of service customers has changed. They are more likely to do an internet search to find a service firm and probably read customer reviews to evaluate their services. This has actually expanded the range of service marketing strategies you have at your disposal.

In summary, in order to remain competitive, you need to regularly monitor your service marketing strategies, evaluate them, and identify areas that need to be improved. It is important to understand that the online and digital marketing industry is evolving much faster than other industries. Service marketing firms emerge as leaders who have successfully collected and used information about their performance - crossing a number of marketing efforts. But a company must have the will to succeed, otherwise no strategy will work.

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